

Mixed ligand complexes of osmium(II/III/IV)-2,2'-dipyridylamine : synthesis and redox behavior

Doyel Bose, Hafijur Rahaman, Jaya Banerjee, Tapan Kumar Mallick, Chittaranjan Sinha and Barindra Kumar Ghosh*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, India

E-mail : barin_1@yahoo.co.uk Fax : 91-342-530452

Manuscript received 27 August 2001, revised 11 February 2002, accepted 25 April 2002

Eight mixed ligand compounds of osmium(II), -(III), -(IV) of general formula, $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2]^{z+}$ [dpya = 2,2'-dipyridylamine; L = 2-(phenylazo)pyridine (L^1), 2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine (L^2), 2,2'-bipyridyl (L^3), quinolin-8-olate (L^4) or 2-methylquinolin-8-olate (L^5); $z = 1-3$] have been prepared, isolated as their perchlorates. The complexes exhibit several spin-allowed and spin-forbidden charge-transfer transitions in the 200–1000 nm region. In MeCN solutions the chelates display $\text{Os}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Os}^{\text{III}}$ and $\text{Os}^{\text{III}}-\text{Os}^{\text{II}}$ couples. The stability of metal oxidation levels is discussed in terms of the electrochemical results and correlated to the π -acceptor properties of these ligands. On the negative side of SCE successive ligand reductions in L^1-L^3 complexes are observable.

The coordination behaviour of 2,2'-dipyridylamine (dpya) has received much attention in recent years¹⁻⁵. A common feature of this ligand is that it can show different ligational behaviours² ranging from monodentate, chelating bidentate and bridging tridentate in mono-, di- and polynuclear complexes. We are currently⁶⁻⁸ investigating the binding of osmium in its different oxidation states through preparation of mixed-ligand complexes of varied ligand strengths. This work stems from our interest in the study of coordination behaviour of dpya in osmium bound state, that remains unexplored to date. In the present work, stable cationic complexes of the type $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2]^{z+}$ [L = 2-(phenylazo)pyridine (L^1), 2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine (L^2), 2,2'-bipyridyl (L^3), quinolin-8-olate (L^4) or 2-methylquinolin-8-olate (L^5); $z = 1$ and 2] (Chart 1) have been isolated as perchlorates

Chart 1

and characterized. The osmium(III) counterparts $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2]^{3+}$ of L^3 and osmium(IV) species $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ of L^4 and L^5 , respectively, are also stable enough for isolation by oxidation with ceric sulfate of their osmium(II) and osmium(III) precursors respectively. However, oxidation of L^1 or L^2 compounds of osmium(II) results in a product of indefinite composition. The chelates provide a unique opportunity for probing redox reactions pertaining to both metal-centred and ligand-based. The details are described below.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of dpya with OsX_2L_2 (X = Cl or Br; L = L^1-L^5) in boiling (b.p. 125°) 2-methoxyethanol-water (2 : 1) through nucleophilic displacement of halide ions and subsequent chelation⁹ by dpya is of general applicability, and proceeds slowly but smoothly. To hasten the reaction, the ligand dpya is used in five-fold excess. The reducing behaviour of the alcoholic solvent converts osmium(IV) to osmium(III) if starting with OsX_2L_2^4 or OsX_2L_2^5 . The presence of water is, however, invariably needed for such mixed ligand tris-complex formation. From the reaction mixture, red-brown, red or orange-red mixed-ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2]^{z+}$ ($z = 2$ for L = L^1-L^3 and $z = 1$ for L = L^4, L^5) are isolated in good yields as crystalline perchlorates. All the crude products were tested by TLC to check presence/absence of dihalogeno precursor. Oxidation of red dication $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ and orange-red monocations

$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^4]^+$ and $[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^5]^+$ by aqueous cerium(IV) sulfate furnishes brown $[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^3]^{3+}$ and green $[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^4]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^5]^{2+}$, respectively; conversion of these to their corresponding precursor complexes can be achieved with hydrazine hydrate. Both oxidative and reductive steps are facile and use of appropriate reagents converts one into the other at room temperature.

The complexes were characterized using microanalytical, spectroscopic, magnetic and electrochemical results (Tables 1 and 2). Analytical data of all the complexes are consistent with the calculated values. The air-stable moisture-insensitive complexes are highly soluble in a range of common organic solvents, such as dichloromethane,

acetonitrile, methanol, ethanol but are moderately soluble in water. In acetonitrile solutions they show¹⁰ the expected 1 : 1, 2 : 1 or 3 : 1 electrolytic behaviour as indicated by their wide range of Λ_M values (Table 1). All the complexes display characteristic ionic perchlorate bands at ~ 1100 (ν_3) and 620 (ν_2), ~ 1590 (C=N) and ~ 3400 cm^{-1} (N-H). In $[\text{Os}^{\text{II}}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^1](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Os}^{\text{II}}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complexes azo mode is observable at ~ 1290 cm^{-1} ; a large shift (140 cm^{-1}) towards lower energy than the free ligand value (1425 cm^{-1})¹¹ is indicative of strong π -bonding of osmium(II) through an azo nitrogen. All other characteristic dpya and L vibrations are present in the 1600 – 600 cm^{-1} range.

Table 1. Physical and spectral (EPR, electronic) data of complexes^a

Compd.	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.	EPR data		λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)
			g_1	g_2	
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^1](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (1)	230	Diamag.	Inactive		825 (960), 740 (1410), 605 (1650), 490, (12010), 344 (20120), 284 (26810), 248 (8940)
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (2)	235	Diamag.	Inactive		828 (980), 742 (1440), 605 (1690), 490 (12230), 344 (20260), 284 (27020), 248 (9150)
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (3)	240	Diamag.	Inactive		930 (720), 765 (940), 614 (2240), 504 (11210), 440 (8160), 395 (11240), 330 (21750), 256 (10230)
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ (4)	320	1.76	2.556	2.168	840 (980), 742 (2390), 618 (2940), 515 (12270), 403 (11870), 362 (27010), 320 (43440), 262 (28660)
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^4](\text{ClO}_4)$ (5)	120	1.78	2.538	2.174	775 (160), 705 (810), 512 (6210), 422 (9620), 350 (14480), 252 (17710)
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^5](\text{ClO}_4)$ (6)	130	1.79	2.561	2.173	778 (190), 710 (840), 510 (6370), 422 (9810), 354 (14860), 252 (18410)
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (7)	240	1.12	Inactive		910 (420), 670 (6810), 510 (4630), 360 (13840), 315 (14780), 255 (21110)
$[\text{Os}(\text{dp}y\text{a})\text{L}_2^5](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (8)	245	1.10	Inactive		920 (450), 672 (6980), 514 (4330), 360 (14770), 315 (15260), 255 (21740)

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Table 2. Electrochemical results in MeCN^a

Compd. no.	E^0 , V (ΔE_p , mV)					
	$\text{Os}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Os}^{\text{III}}$	$\text{Os}^{\text{III}}\text{-Os}^{\text{II}}$	r_1	r_2	r_3	r_4^b
1	<i>a</i>	1.51 (90)	-0.26 (60)	-0.62 (70)	-1.49 (100)	-1.72
2	<i>a</i>	1.53 (90)	-0.28 (60)	-0.65 (70)	-1.51 (100)	-1.78
3	1.58 (90)	0.41 (60)	-1.23 (90)	-1.55 (100)	-2.16 ^b	<i>a</i>
4	1.59 (90)	0.41 (60)	-1.24 (90)	-1.54 (100)	-2.18 ^b	<i>a</i>
5	0.68 (70)	-0.42 (60)	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>
6	0.65 (70)	-0.44 (60)	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>
7	0.68 (70)	-0.42 (60)	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>
8	0.64 (70)	-0.44 (60)	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>

^aMeaning of units and symbol are the same as in text; Unless otherwise stated both CV and DPV results are listed; working electrode is platinum.

^aNot observable. ^bDPV results only.

The magnetic susceptibility data (Table 1) show that the osmium(II) complexes are uniformly diamagnetic (t_{2g}^6 idealised, $S = 0$) and osmium(III) chelates have moments close to the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) expected for mononuclear low-spin (t_{2g}^5 idealised, $S = 1/2$) six-coordinate d^5 -complexes. Osmium(IV) complexes exhibit a sub-normal magnetic moment (1.1 B.M.); such a low value with t_{2g}^4 configuration is characteristic of heavy metal osmium in octahedral environment¹². All the osmium(II) and osmium(IV) complexes are EPR-silent at room temperature and liquid nitrogen in MeCN-PhMe solution and glass, respectively, as expected^{13,14} for d^6 and d^4 metal ions, respectively. On the other hand, in MeCN-PhMe glass at liquid nitrogen temperature (-196°), two resonances are observable for the osmium(III) complexes (Table 1). The inability to observe an expected third resonance is often a characteristic feature^{15,16} of an anisotropic environment in low-spin d^5 -osmium complexes. No ligand hyperfine structure could be resolved in any of the spectra.

The complexes exhibit several absorption bands and shoulders in the 200–1000 nm region (Table 1). The high intensity bands below 400 nm are presumably of ligand origin assignable to intraligand $n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions. Above this wavelength the transitions are LMCT for osmium(III)/osmium(IV) complexes and MLCT type for osmium(II) members. The intense transitions are spin-allowed whilst the weaker ones at longer wavelengths could be of spin-forbidden being partially allowed through strong spin-orbit coupling by heavy element osmium^{17,18}.

The electroactivity of the complexes was examined in MeCN solutions using voltammetry (CV and DPV) and coulometry at platinum and glassy carbon electrodes. The DPV technique is particularly useful for observing responses close to solvent cut-off regions. Essentially the same voltammogram (CV and DPV) is observable irrespective of whether the bulk solutions contain mixed $dpya-L^3$ complex on +2 or +3 level and mixed $dpya-L^4/L^5$ complexes on +3 or +4 level. The results are summarized in Table 2 and representative voltammograms are shown in Fig. 1. In acetonitrile the chelates display two successive nearly reversible CV responses for mixed $dpya-L^3$ and $dpya-L^4/L^5$ complexes which correspond to osmium(III)-osmium(II) and osmium(IV)-osmium(III) couples, whereas the mixed $dpya-L^1/L^2$ complexes show only the former couple. The responses (eqs. 1 and 2, shown with $L = L^3$),

are reproducible with no trace of decomposition after a num-

Fig. 1. CV (—) and DPV (-----) of (a) $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (2) and (b) $[\text{Os}(\text{dpya})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (3) in MeCN solution ($\gamma = 10 \mu\text{A}$ for CV and $5 \mu\text{A}$ for DPV).

ber of cycles. One-electron nature of couple 1 was confirmed from constant-potential electrolysis ($n = 1.02$) and that of 2 from a comparison of current height with couple 1 in DPV experiments.

The most striking observation is the almost 1 V positive shift of the potential in $\text{Os}^{\text{III}}-\text{Os}^{\text{II}}$ couple in passing from L^4/L^5 complexes to L^3 compound and another 1 V shift towards anodic potential from L^3 to L^1/L^2 compounds. This is in accord with argument that $d\pi(t_{2g})$ level (HOMO) of metal orbital in azoimine (L^1/L^2) complexes is most stabilized. Strong π -back-donation of the metal to the excellent¹⁹ π -acceptor azoimine ligand is no doubt the prime factor in making E^0 of the metal-based electrode reactions high. Although the overall charges have some effect, the trend in such E^0 values dictates the order of π -acceptor ability as $L^4/L^5 < L^3 < L^1/L^2$. The presence of one pyridine N (π -acceptor centre) and one phenolic O (with almost no π -acceptance property) in L^4/L^5 , two pyridine N's (both π -acceptor centres) in L^3 , and one pyridine N (π -acceptor centre) and one azo N (excellent¹⁹ π -acceptor centre) in L^1/L^2 may presumably control the π -acceptor ability.

The negative side of SCE was scanned using a glassy carbon electrode. The LUMO (π^* level) of L ($L = L^1-L^3$) can accommodate¹⁹ upto two electrons. Four successive one-electron reductions are therefore expected for OsL_2^{2+} ($L = L^1-L^3$) moiety. In the potential range -0.3 to -2.2 V, three reductions are seen in CV but all the four expected reductions are clearly observable in careful DPV experiments in dry solvents. The first two reductions are reproducible (in CV) with current height comparable to that of couple 1,

indicating involvement of one-electron transfer. The redox processes are depicted in eqs. (3) and (4),

The third reduction in L^3 and fourth L^1/L^2 are irreversible in CV, which may be due to some kind of chemical assistance²⁰ connected with the charge transfer steps at such lower potentials. The reductions in L^3 complexes involve diimine ($-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) fragment whereas azoimine ($-\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) moiety of L^1/L^2 carries electron mainly in the azo part^{11,19}. That the π^* (azo) orbital in L^1/L^2 is substantially more stable²¹ than the π^* (Ψ) orbital of L^3 is reflected by the more anodic value of the first reduction potential. The same relationship also holds in free¹⁹ ligands ($E^0 = -1.31$ V for L^1 and -2.21 V for L^3). The more effective charge on azo ($-\text{N}=\text{N}-$) over imine ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) is the major responsible factor in stabilizing LUMO of L^1/L^2 complexes containing azoimine than that of L^3 ones containing diimine. It may be noted that the free ligands dpya, L^4 and L^5 do not show any response in the whole potential window used in studying the complexes, which is helpful in assigning the responses on the negative of SCE in L^4 and L^5 complexes to be metal centred.

We conclude that this study has addressed a comparative account of L^1/L^2 , L^3 and L^4/L^5 towards Os-dpva binding. Electrochemical results are particularly useful in analyzing their chemistry. The results reflect that of the three azoimines stabilize osmium(II) the most, quinolin-8-olate the least and diimine has in between behaviour. To our knowledge this work demonstrates the first example where the comparative view of osmium-dpva binding in different oxidation states of the metal has been examined in combination with diimine, azoimine or quinolin-8-olate.

Experimental

A reported method¹¹ was used to obtain the azoimine ligands (L). OsX_2L_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br ; $\text{L} = \text{L}^1-\text{L}^5$) complexes were prepared by the literature methods^{9,15}. Purification of solvent (MeCN) and preparation of the supporting electrolyte ($[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$) for electrochemical work were executed following published procedure²². 2,2'-Bipyridyl, 2,2'-dipyridylamine, quinolin-8-ol, 2-methylquinolin-8-ol and all other chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade and used as such. All the synthetic reactions and final work-up were done in air.

Caution! Perchlorates of heavy metal ions with organic ligands are potentially explosive. The syntheses described below involve the use of perchlorate ions and isolation of

the complex cations as perchlorate salts. Such a procedure may present an explosion hazard and due care should be exercised to avoid this, although we did not encounter any problem by taking small quantity of the samples.

Electrical conductivities (in MeCN, solute $\sim 10^{-3}$ M, at 25°), electronic (in MeCN, solute $\sim 10^{-3}$ M) and IR (KBr, 4000–600 cm^{-1} ; polyethylene, 600–300 cm^{-1}) spectra were recorded using a Systronics 304 direct reading conductometer, Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer and Jasco FTIR 420 spectrometer, respectively. Magnetic susceptibility (in solid state) was measured at 25° with a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer. EPR spectra (in 1 : 1 MeCN-PhMe) were run on a Varian 109C E-line X-band spectrometer fitted with a quartz Dewar for measurements at -196° (liquid nitrogen); all spectra were calibrated with the help of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl ($g = 2.0037$). Microanalyses (C, H and N) were done with a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. Electrochemical studies were performed (in MeCN at 25°) under dry N_2 with a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system as described elsewhere⁸. In cyclic voltammetry (CV), the following parameters and relation were used; scan rate (ν), 50 mV s^{-1} ; formal potential, $E^0 = 0.5 (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})$, where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials, respectively; ΔE_{p} is the peak-to-peak separation; and in differential pulse voltammetry (DPV): scan rate (ν), 10 mV s^{-1} ; modulation amplitude (ΔE), 25 mV ; $E^0 = E_{\text{p}} + 0.5 (\Delta E)$, where E_{p} is the DPV peak potential. The agreement between E^0 data obtained by the two techniques was good (within ± 5 mV). The potentials are referenced to a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and are uncorrected for the junction contributions.

Preparation of complexes :

$[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2]^{z+}$ ($z = 1$ or 2) complexes were prepared using a general procedure. The bromo over chloro compounds were taken as starting materials as the former is better leaving group. Oxidation of $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2]^{z+}$ ($\text{L} = \text{L}^3$, $z = 2$; $\text{L} = \text{L}^4$ or L^5 ; $z = 1$) and the conversion of the oxidized species to reduced homologs are also described. The synthetic details for a particular compound in each case are given below. Yields varied in the range 60–75%.

$[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^1](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: To a suspension of $\text{OsBr}_2\text{L}_2^1$ (100 mg, 0.14 mmol) in $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 : 1; 30 ml) was added dpva (120 mg, 0.701 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The initial blue-violet solution that changed to red-brown was filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was washed copiously with Et_2O , dissolved in ethanol-water (10 ml) saturated with NaClO_4 and evaporated. The precipitate was dried *in vacuo*, redissolved in a minimum of CH_2Cl_2 and loaded on a silica

gel (60–120 mesh) column (20 × 1 cm). A small blue-violet band of unreacted $\text{OsBr}_2\text{L}_2^1$ was eluted first with CH_2Cl_2 . Finally, the slow moving red-brown band of the desired compound was collected with Ph-MeCN (4 : 1). Slow evaporation of this solution resulted in dark red crystals that were washed with chilled H_2O and dried *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} to yield analytically pure desired product (78 mg, 60%). $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ was prepared (yield, 62%) similarly except that $\text{OsBr}_2\text{L}_2^2$ was used instead of $\text{OsBr}_2\text{L}_2^1$.

$[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: dpva (126 mg, 0.736 mmol) was added to a solution of $\text{OsBr}_2\text{L}_2^3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (100 mg, 0.147 mmol) in $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 : 1, 15 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The red solution was filtered and evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath. The solid mass was washed several times with toluene to remove excess ligand. It was then dissolved in ethanol-water (10 ml) saturated with NaClO_4 and the solution was evaporated slowly in air. The resultant solid was washed with cold water and Et_2O and dried *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} to have analytically pure desired product (90 mg, 70%).

$[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^4]\text{ClO}_4$: To a suspension of $\text{OsBr}_2\text{L}_2^4$ (100 mg, 0.157 mmol) in $\text{MeOCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 : 1; 15 ml) was added dpva (134 mg, 0.783 mmol), and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. An orange-red solution was obtained which on evaporation under reduced pressure gave a dark residue. It was washed with solvent ether and dried *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} . The solid was dissolved in ethanol-water (10 ml) saturated with NaClO_4 , evaporated slowly in air, redissolved in a minimum of CH_2Cl_2 and chromatographed as described in $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^1](\text{ClO}_4)_2$. At first a green fraction of unreacted $\text{OsBr}_2\text{L}_2^4$ was eluted with CH_2Cl_2 followed by a slow moving band eluted with PhH-MeCN (2 : 1). On slow evaporation of the latter, crystals of the desired compound resulted (76 mg, 65%). $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^5]\text{ClO}_4$ was prepared similarly (68%).

$[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$: A solution of $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (100 mg, 0.115 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 -MeCN (1 : 1; 15 ml) was stirred magnetically at room temperature (25°). To it was added dropwise aqueous $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (56 mg, 0.139 mmol in 1 M H_2SO_4) solution (10 ml). The red solution immediately changed to red-brown. The stirring was continued for further 15 min and the solution was filtered. The filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was dried. The mass was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 5 cm³), the solution was allowed to evaporate in air and the solid redissolved in MeCN. A saturated aqueous solution (2 ml) of NaClO_4 was added to it and the solution was concentrated and kept overnight in refrigerator. The dark crystalline product that separated was washed with cold

water and dried *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} , (78 mg, 70%).

$[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: It was prepared similarly using the same stoichiometry and conditions as described above in $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ except that $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^4]\text{ClO}_4$ was used instead of $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$. The yield of the green compound was 75%; $[\text{Os}(\text{dpva})\text{L}_2^5](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ was also prepared (72%) similarly.

Conversion of $\text{Os}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{Os}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Os}^{\text{IV}} \rightarrow \text{Os}^{\text{III}}$: Osmium(IV) or osmium(III) compound (0.1 mmol) was dissolved in MeCN (10 ml) and the solution was stirred magnetically at 25°. $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.15 mmol) in MeCN was then added to it dropwise. The green osmium(IV) solution changed to orange-red, whereas red-brown osmium(III) solution changed to red. On evaporation under reduced pressure, dark solids that deposited were extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 5 ml). On slow evaporation of these extracts, pure osmium(III) and osmium(II) (whichever the case) were obtained in an almost quantitative yield. Analytically pure materials were obtained after recrystallization from MeCN- H_2O followed by drying *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} . The composition was checked by comparing properties with authentic samples of osmium(III) and osmium(II) compounds.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged. Two of the authors (D.B. and H.R.) are respectively thankful to C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi, respectively for fellowships. The authors are also indebted to Professor A. Chakravorty, Kolkata, for spectroscopic and electrochemical work.

References

1. A. Campus, N. Marsich, A. M. M. Lanfredi, F. Uguzzoli and C. Massera, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2000, **309**, 1; S. Youngme, C. Pakawatchai, W. Somjitsripunya, K. Chinnakali and H. -K. Fun, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2000, **303**, 181.
2. F. A. Cotton, L. M. Daniels and G. T. Jordan IV, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1997, 421; F. A. Cotton, L. M. Daniels, G. T. Jordan IV and C. A. Murillo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 10377; E. -C. Yang, M. -C. Cheng, M. -S. Tsai and S. -M. Peng, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 2377.
3. G. J. Pyrka, M. El-Mekki and A. A. Pinkerton, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 84; L. -P. Wu, P. Field, T. Morrissey, C. Murphy, P. Nagle, B. Hathaway, C. Simmons and P. Thornton, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 3835.
4. J. Chin, V. Jubian and K. Mrejen, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 1326; D. E. Morris, Y. Ohsaur, D. P. Segers, M. K. DeArmond and K. W. Hanck, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 3010; W. L. Huang, D. P. Segers and M. K. DeArmond, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 2080; O. R. Rodig, T. Brueckner, B. K. Huriburt, R. K. Schlatter, T. L. Benable and E. Sinn, *J. Chem.*

- Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 196; C. E. Baxxter, O. R. Rodig, R. K. Schlatzer and E. Sinn, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 1918.
5. K. D. Karlin, J. C. Hayes, Y. Gultneh, R. W. Cruse, J. W. McKown, J. P. Hutchinson and J. Zubieta, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 2121; V. McKee, J. V. Daggigian, R. Bau and C. A. Reed, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 7000.
 6. B. K. Roy, T. K. Mallick and B. K. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 1992, **11**, 1829; B. K. Roy, P. K. Das, T. K. Mallick and B. K. Ghosh, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1993, 154; T. K. Mallick, P. K. Das, S. Sinha and B. K. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 1994, **13**, 1817.
 7. S. Sinha, P. K. Das and B. K. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1995, **20**, 59; P. R. Basudhar, S. Sinha, P. K. Das and B. K. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 154; S. Sinha, A. K. Banerjee and B. K. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 483.
 8. P. K. Das, S. Sinha and B. K. Ghosh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 586; S. Sinha, A. K. Banerjee and B. K. Ghosh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 264; N. K. Mondal, P. K. Das, B. K. Roy and B. K. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1999, **24**, 678.
 9. D. A. Buckingham, F. P. Dwyer, H. A. Goodwin and A. M. Sargeson, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 325; B. K. Ghosh, A. Mukhopadhyay, S. Goswami, S. Ray and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 4633.
 10. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
 11. R. A. Krause and K. Krause, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 2600; 1982, **21**, 1714.
 12. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 5th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1988, p. 632.
 13. R. S. Drago, "Physical Methods in Chemistry", Saunders, London, 1977, p. 492.
 14. S. L. Dexheimer, J. W. Gohdes, M. K. Chan, K. S. Hagen, W. H. Armstrong and M. P. Klein, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 8923.
 15. G. K. Lahiri, S. Bhattacharya, B. K. Ghosh and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 4324.
 16. E. M. Kober and T. J. Meyer, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 1614; R. E. DeSimone and R. S. Drago, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 2343; M. -A. Haga, K. Isobe, S. R. Boone and C. G. Pierpont, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 3795.
 17. B. J. Pankuch, D. E. Lacky and G. A. Crosby, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1980, **84**, 2061; S. Decurtins, F. Felix, J. Ferguson, H. U. Gudel and A. Ludi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 4102.
 18. E. M. Kober and T. J. Meyer, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 3967.
 19. B. K. Ghosh and A. Chakravorty, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **95**, 239.
 20. J. Heinze, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1984, **23**, 831.
 21. A. Ceulemans and L. G. Vanquickenborne, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 2238.
 22. D. T. Sawyer and J. L. Roberts, Jr, "Experimental Electrochemistry for Chemists", Wiley, New York, 1974, p. 167.